

RoguePlots_CBI-24-Mol: This pdf contains the RoguePlots created for the 24 fossils resulting from the constrained Bayesian Inference analysis for 24 fossils using only molecular data (fossils under the prior) (CBI-24-Mol).

Figure	page
S1g.Rogue_plotX_Archaenthus_linnenbergeri	2
S2g.Rogue_plotX_Archaestella_verticillatus	3
S3g.Rogue_plotX_Bertilanthus_scanicus	4
S4g.Rogue_plotX_Canrightia_resinifera	5
S5g.Rogue_plotX_Carpestella_lacunata	6
S6g.Rogue_plotX_Cecilanthus_polymerus	7
S7g.Rogue_plotX_Chloranthistemon_endressii	8
S8g.Rogue_plotX_Dakotanthus_cordiformis	9
S9g.Rogue_plotX_Divisestylus_brevistamineus	10
S10g.Rogue_plotX_Florissantia_quilchenensis	11
S11g.Rogue_plotX_Kajanthus_lusitanicus	12
S12g.Rogue_plotX_Mabelia_connatifila	13
S13g.Rogue_plotX_Mauldinia_mirabilis	14
S14g.Rogue_plotX_Microvictoria_svitkoana	15
S15g.Rogue_plotX_Paleoclusia_chevalieri	16
S16g.Rogue_plotX_Paradinandra_suecica	17
S17g.Rogue_plotX_Pentapetalum_trifasciculandricus	18
S18g.Rogue_plotX_Platydiscus_peltatus	19
S19g.Rogue_plotX_Quadriplatanus_georgianus	20
S20g.Rogue_plotX_Rariglanda_jerseyensis	21
S21g.Rogue_plotX_Saururus_tuckerae	22
S22g.Rogue_plotX_Spanomera_mauldinensis	23
S23g.Rogue_plotX_Tylerianthus_crossmanensis	24
S24g.Rogue_plotX_Virginianthus_calycanthoides	25

X_Archaeanthus_linnenbergeri

PP

X_Archaestella_verticillatus

PP

X_Bertilanthus_scanicus

PP

X_Canrightia_resinifera

PP

X_Carpestella_lacunata

PP

X_Cecilanthus_polymerus

PP

X_Chloranthistemon_endressii

PP

X_Dakotanthus_cordiformis

PP

X_Divisestylus_brevistamineus

PP

X_Florissantia_quilchenensis

PP

X_Kajanthus_lusitanicus

PP

X_Mabelia_connatifila

PP

X_Mauldinia_mirabilis

PP

X_Microvictoria_svitkoana

PP

X_Paleocclusia_chevalieri

PP

X_Paradinandra_suecica

PP

X_Pentapetalum_trifasciculandricus

PP

X_Platydiscus_peltatus

PP

X_Quadriplatanus_georgianus

PP

X_Rariglanda_jerseyensis

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